

Community Participation: An Alternative for Proper School Management in Nigeria

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Abstract

Education is a powerful catalysing agent and it plays a pivotal role in the development of individuals, community as well as society. Education ranks at the near top in the social priorities of all countries. Education is a social process and it receives its meaning and essential logic from the society of which it is a part. In modern societies, education is considered as an indispensable requirement of development and a fundamental right of every individual. Education cannot be provided without proper management and proper management cannot be done without a proper strategy. Therefore, to shade light on proper strategies for school management, community participation: an alternative for proper school management in Nigeria. The objectives of this paper should intend to propose a better way of managing schools for better educational input and out for national development with community participation as the alternative. This paper highlights the concept of community participation, concept of educational management, concept of decentralization in educational management, need for community participation in school management in Nigeria, conclusion and recommendations as sub-headings in the paper. Descriptive method, surveying the literature was employed as the research method. One of the findings, among others, is that community participation helps in designing proper school curriculum and handling school resources with the required probity and accountability. It is recommended among others, that media, print, electronic and social should be used by government and community leaders in promoting community participation in school management.

Keyword: community, participation, decentralization, school management & alternative.

Introduction

Education is a life-long process through which the individual acquires the relevant skills and knowledge which enable him to be useful to himself and community. Education serves as the cornerstone of societal development, playing a pivotal role in shaping individuals and preparing them for active participation in the community, (Fagerlind and Saha 2023). Education is multifaceted in nature and transcends the mere transmission of knowledge; it encompasses the cultivation of skills, values, and critical thinking abilities, contributing to the holistic development of individuals and society. In the new world order impacted by internet and digital technologies, education prepares individuals for life and provides them the skills to navigate the complexities of the inter-relations between man and his environment (Saha 2023).

Against this backdrop, educational institutions from lower-level schools (particularly at secondary school level) to tertiary or universities require a strong and focused leadership to forge a school climate within the components that constitute an effective and efficient learning environment. Education management is the coordination of policies, curriculum development, human resources, finances, and community engagement to create a conducive space for educators and learners, (Medina, Cosby, & Grim 2020). An important component of education management is community participation, since education is a collective endeavor; fostering community involvement is an integral and critical component of the educational system. Community participation in education management is the active engagement of parents, local community or residents within and around the school and various stakeholders in decision-making, planning, and support for educational venture, (Kusumaningrum, Ulfatin, Maisyaroh, Triwiyanto, & Gunawan, 2024). This collaborative approach underscores the interdependence between educational institutions (like secondary schools) and the communities they serve, thus, reinforcing shared responsibility for the success of the educational enterprise. The interconnection and relationship between education, education management and community participation are very essential for the creation of a dynamic, inclusive and responsive learning environment (Kusumaningrum et al., 2024). Understanding these relationships can enhance the quality of education, promote students' success and contribute to the development of the broader society. A comprehensive exegesis of the models that explains different strategies and approaches to facilitate effective community participation at secondary school level of education management is therefore significant.

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2024) defined Model as usually miniature representation of something; a pattern of something to be made; a type or design of product; an example for imitation or emulation and a set of plans for a building. In education management, model refers to a structured and systematic representation or framework that describes, guides, and prescribes the processes, interactions and elements involved in managing educational institutions, (Bush, 2020; Ghasemy, & Hussin, 2021). Model in the context of this paper refers to a means of explanation and or imitation for good way of managing education system. Over the years, some models of community participation in education management have emerged in different communities and have gained popularity and significance in the community practice field (Mukhtar, 2021). These models include Goodland, J. Model, Bhusham S. Model and Ubuntu Theory of Management. Because of their popularity and significance, these models appear to be some of the most prominent in community participation discourse and practice.

Based on the critical role these models play in understanding the different phenomenon in community participation practice in education, this paper aims to deconstruct the models in the context of Nigerian education system at secondary school level. The significance of this exegesis is to contribute to better understanding of the different models in shaping the policy, and practice of community participation in educational management at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. In addition, a brief review of the literature shows a lack of focus in that direction thus, serving as a contribution to the body of knowledge in that regard. Consequently, the details in the paper will serve as an adroit cudgel for educationist, educators, education managers and relevant stakeholders in the Nigerian education ecosystem.

Community participation refers to the involvement of community members through a platform like Community Promotion Committee (CPC), School-Based Management Committee (SBMC), and Old Students Association, in order to get engaged in things that matter in the development of the community. An example of the things is educational management (Mukhtar, 2021). Every faction of society plays its role in children education, in one way or the other. Efforts must be undertaken to join together the efforts for better yields. That can be effectively done if there is effective collaboration between schools, parents and other community groups. It is very important to understand that the community participation must not be the goal in spreading of education; neither can it miraculously solve education issues, especially in developing countries. It can only facilitate the process of improving the educational standards and promotion of democracy in society (World Bank, 2020). Recognized parent and community support as one of the key factors to determine school effectiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Epstein (2022) focuses on how to help children succeed in school and later life by involving partnerships of schools, families and communities who help in improving school programmes and environment, provide family services, increase parents' skills and leadership, liaise with other communities and help teachers with their work. Epstein (2022) concludes by spelling out various methods by which families and communities can work together. These are: -

1. **Parenting:** Responsible parenting is the best means to create education supportive environment for children at home.
2. **Communicating:** Through effective communication, parents can interact better with teachers. They can know more about school education programmes and education process.
3. **Volunteering:** Parent's help can be recruited and incorporated through parent help and support.
4. **Decision Making:** Inclusion of parents' ideas in school decision making process.

Community involvement can help promotion of education in a number of ways. Few ways out of these as described by Grim, (2020)) are appended below:

1. Encouraging regular attendance of students
2. Monitor teachers' attendance and efficiency.
3. frequently arrange and attend school meetings
4. Make teachers feel secure by constructing accommodation for them
5. Organize school events calendars

Community driven development intervention, which includes community participation in the management of education, is justified of its capacity to exclude people at the grassroots level from poverty and get them better economic status and social development (Grim, (2020). Thus, community participation can play a vital role in facilitating the process of improving the educational standards and promotion of democracy in educational institutions. Additionally, it will help much in the giving financial and material support, boosting the morale of the students in school and designing curriculum that conforms to the norms and values of the community. Therefore, community participation refers to the involvement of the local community members in deciding and acting on issues that matter in having a better life for individual and collective members of the community (Medina, 2020).

Management refers to the set of actions taken and activities that are made in order to achieve a given objective or attain at a certain goal. Therefore, educational management is a set of actions being taken and activities being carried-out

towards achieving the school and educational system aims and objectives of given community or country (Cosby,2020). Much of the literature deals with interaction of managers and their subordinates with the environment inside the enterprise, but in most instances the effective manager must also deal with the outside environment. Every time the manager plan, they take into account the needs and desires of members of society, outside the organization, as well as the needs for material and human resources, technology and other requirements in the external requirements, in the external environment. All managers, whether they operate in business, a government agency, a charitable foundation, a school or a university, must in a varying degree, take into account the elements and forces of their external environment. They must identify, evaluate and react to the forces of outside the organization that may affect its operations. Community being one of those forces has to be considered in managing schools. Therefore, the main concern of management is to establish a link between the stakeholders, the activities they do and the resources they have towards achieving the stated goal. An example of this stated goal is providing better education for the school children. Decision making is a key management element because managers continually face decisions in planning; organising, leading and controlling that affect the organisation and its performance. A decision is the choice made from among available alternatives that expected to result in a favourable resolution of a problem.

Therefore, educational management refers to the effective and efficient co-ordination, controlling, guiding and equitably and equally providing and sharing of both human and material resources in educational organisation with a view to achieving the aims and objectives of the organisation. Something of relevance and importance in effective educational management is considering the external environment to the educational organisation because the external environment influences the educational organisation and can play a very vital and viable role in its progress and development. This shows the relevance and importance of community participation in the management of educational institutions (Grim, (2021).

According Karstanje (2021), in Western, Central and Eastern Europe, decentralization involves the assignment to local council level, shortening the distance between the-government and the school. Community is involved in decision making wherever possible with the participation of those affected by the decision. There are school councils within the schools comprised of representatives from the ranks of teachers, parents, pupils and the general public. These councils play an important part in matters such as curriculum development, pupil admission, criteria for passing and much more.

Some of the noteworthy trends that educational management in modern times exhibits as stated by (Karstanje, 2021) are as follow:

1. Educational policy, curriculum, teaching methods, examination or books should be framed or decided upon at the lowest of the institutional level, it is a response to aspiration for freedom. These are liberating trends which may pave way for a new society. But the assumption here, is that teachers and heads at all levels of the education ladder are alive to conditions and needs of the community as also to new knowledge emerging at a fast rate (Karstanje,2021)).
2. To execute educational strategies, we must identify, stimulate and experiment with innovations, administration and management of educational systems and launch a search for the means of financing education. A major limitation is that education all over the world has received far limited resources than any other sphere of activity (Karstanje, 2021).
3. Decentralization must be permitted in respect of making, responsibility and resources at all levels to ensure the participation of all concerned: teachers' community, educational experts, parents in determining and carrying out educational activity.
4. Educational management should be democratized and general public should be allowed a considerable say in all decisions affecting education (Karstanje, 2021)).

Quality education should be the target for educational administrators. A periodical evaluation of the system of education as it is operating and of the system of educational management as it exists should, therefore, be conducted to examine whether the target is achieved, and if so to what extent.

Therefore, as explained by Karstanje,(2021), it is also pertinent to understand that the concentration of powers in decision making, providing for infrastructural facilities, curriculum development, staff welfare and training and so on, in the hands of only government leads to menaces like not being able to effectively and efficiently deliver for educational development by the government. Thus, this leads to decay in the system of education. This is as we are seeing practically in Nigeria where government could not due as expected due to the burden that over-weighs her shoulder. Therefore, to deal with the situation decentralization could be the answer. By decentralization the government is being relieved of the burden that over weighs her shoulder and better management results and returns are yielded. Decentralization means the sharing of decision making power and educational burdens by the government with the other stakeholders and particularly the community (Karstanje, 2021).

The main aim of any exercise which is jointly carried out by parents and the community, with regards to education, is to make the learning process so effective that an increased number of children are imparted knowledge, according to the globalized world scenario. There are certain convincing factors which favour community participation in education activity.

The factors are as mentioned and explained by Goldring (2020) as follow:

Governments world over are making efforts to spread as much education they can. In reality, most of the governments fail to achieve this aim for numerous reasons like lack of capital and resources. Everywhere, there is shortage of trained teachers, especially in the third world countries. Therefore, the only way for planners to deliberate, is to chalk out effective and efficient means of utilizing whatever available resources they have. World Bank Report of 2020 deliberated upon “Case Study Madagascar”. In Madagascar, government patronage in terms of investment and budget is extremely low. Communities were found contributing to the maximum extent mainly in impartation of primary education. Community and parents look after the school infrastructures, equipment and educational supplies, in order to keep the education process going.

Incorporation of communities and parents normally results in defining relevant curricula, which is more pertinent to the local society. Local communities understand their societies in a much better way, as compared to planners sitting far away. A case study in Papua New Guinea conducted by Ajmal, (2021), highlights community schools which have set a goal to establish a close link between education and local culture. As a result, the community schools’ curriculum was given due place in national curricula. Cultural traditions like festivals, customs and events etc are effectively promoted through education. (Grim, 2020) narrate another case example of “Escuela Nueva Programme” undertaken in Columbia. In this programme a very large share is given to community participation in preparation of curricula. The curriculum so designed, includes self-instructional textbooks containing information about local cultural elements. They also include oral traditions on local crafts, economic activities, health problems, geography, sports, local music and dances. Students benefiting from Escuela Nueva Programme find themselves gaining education, as well as their cultural and traditional knowledge. The students were found well aware of their values, which they could effectively utilise, when they themselves become part of their communities (Perkins, 2021).

The role of local communities could also be pronounced in finding out problems which hinder the educational process, such as low participation and weak academic performance. A case study in Gambia, as reported by Grim, (2020)) focused on low attendance of girls in the schools. A new technique called Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) was incorporated. In this technique, efforts were launched to mobilize the community in creating awareness and assisting them to come out with their own solutions. Models of thirteen locals were trained about PRA objectives. Participation from all community groups like literate and illiterate, young and old, men and women were incorporated. Seven rural villages were earmarked for the activity where PRA trained teams focused on villagers by discussing about their issues including income and expenditure and education related issues. This report discovered following reasons which were adversely effecting girls’ education:-

1. Acute shortage of books
2. High schooling cost
3. Higher risk of teenage pregnancy
4. Social taboos like expected loss of traditional values, like family obedience
5. Incorrect perceptions among men that girls are less successful in life

Best solution to enhance the female schooling is to involve the parents into the activities of community schools. It could also help in identifying potential teachers. A local woman identified as a potential teacher, can greatly help in girls’ education activity. Apart from this, local notables, elders and religious leaders who are respected by the community, could be incorporated to convince the parents to send their girls to school (Grim, (2020).

Epstein (2022) argues that there are certain ways to create effective parents-community-school partnerships. Some of these are:-

1. Reducing discontinuities between schools and families
2. Eliminating any differences between schools and communities, schools and families, teachers and parents
3. Reduce objections, if any over the syllabi
4. Making easy transition of students going from home to school
5. Preparing students to engage in learning process
6. Minimizing cultural shock of new entrants to schools

Case Study example of Social Forestry Education and Participation Pilot Project (SFEPPP) in Thailand is very relevant here. It aimed to change learning and school-community relations by incorporating fifth and sixth grade students. The students were tasked to study forest management which they did by visiting farms and questioning the foresters. The local community greatly helped them understand the concepts which they had studied in schools. Apart from this, the students also studied animals and plants as part of their regular science curricula. There also, the locals provided them with expert views. When the

project was examined by McDonough and Wheeler (2023), it was found that the communities had greatly contributed in education of their youth. It was also found that the curriculum could be linked to daily life and environment to be more effective.

The involvement of parents in education process is regarded as a proper democratic value in some countries. (Goldring, 2020), highlights that in Denmark, England and Wales, parents have a proper right of being represented at the school governing bodies. In France the parents have rights to representation of entire policy making and planning bodies. The Spanish Constitution defines rights of teachers, parents and students allowing their participation in entire education service. Many other European states have similar democratic systems in place.

Sustainability is a basic requirement for a school to function. Budget availability is the basic factor to keep the schools running. The budget is provided by government funding, private funding, donations from donor societies and philanthropists or local contribution. Community participation alone cannot assure prolonged sustainability, as the communities have to rely on external funding of some form to keep the schools running. However, the purpose of involving the community in supervisory or monitoring role is to ensure that the external funds are judiciously utilized. In this way whatever self-generation and judicious use become two means to effectively undertake prolonged sustainability even if the external interventions are stopped. Thus, self-reliance is achieved (Ajmal, 2021). Effective community participation should not be restricted to schooling and education only. It can also contribute in improving home environment and views of parents. It can make parents understand the benefits of education for their children and also encourage parents to send their children to schools. World Bank (2020) study for India analyzing primary education system, narrates that families aware of the importance of children education, even in the under-developing regions can contribute more effectively in the education process. Those were found achieving better grades, whose parents helped them by providing time and environment for study, encouraged reading and supported their educational desires. It is generally found that the families which are closely involved in schooling and education process not only have a better understanding of education, but are also more willing to cooperate in improving children's learning. In their individual capacity too, such parents can help their children by providing conducive environment and study materials at home.

While viewing different forms of community support, we find that some are clearly designed to support teachers. As an example, constructing houses for teachers working away from that community is one form of support. Such a support would be ideally suited in rural areas, which are generally devoid of such facilities. A qualified teacher would feel more at ease while going to a rural school where he is being provided accommodation. Language barrier is yet another issue which can hinder teacher-student relationship, especially if the teachers are not native. The community members can very effectively contribute by explaining to the students in local dialects, the teachers lecture. In this way a big gap between teachers and students can be filled, and both the teachers and students can feel more bonded. Community can also contribute by providing them knowledge and information about the local region (Medina, 2020).

Conclusion

Community participation will go a long way in supplementing the effort of government in providing citizens with better education. It will also play a significant role in graduating better products from our schools. It also promotes the democratic value in decision making in education in the sense that it provides citizens with the opportunity to partake in determining things that matter to their life, education for example. Therefore, the paper concludes that community participation is a better alternative for proper school management in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The paper recommends, on the basis of what has been discussed, as follows:

1. Government should encourage community participation in school management
2. To encourage community participation in school management, government should wage an awareness creation and sensitisation campaign on the importance and significance of community participation in school management
3. Community leaders should work assiduously in enjoining their community members to get involved in school management activities, particularly in schools in and around their communities.
4. Print, electronic and social media should be used by government and community leaders in promoting community participation in school management.

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